

Maritime World Model for Data-Based Threat Assessment

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Abstract—Maritime security is becoming increasingly important due to recent damage to critical infrastructures. The collision of the ship *Petra L* with an offshore wind turbine has shown that too many alarms causes them to be switched off. It is therefore mandatory to assess situations to determine whether they pose a threat. To assess different threat scenarios, a world model (WM) is required to perceive the environment as a first step. This is the first phase of the concept of situation awareness. In the second and third phases, situations are assessed whether they pose a threat and future threats are predicted based on the current situation. For the latter two phases, instruments for assessing the situation must be developed in the future. There are various maritime WMs to model the maritime world, but they do not provide all the required information about ship information such as flag state, and synthetic data from constructive simulations are not considered. This paper shows the developed WM, how the data are stored and how it can provide information for threat assessment. It also describes how synthetic data can be integrated into a WM.

Index Terms—world model, situation awareness, maritime security.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime security is becoming increasingly important as ship movements or divers can pose a physical threat to critical infrastructures. Recent incidents such as the damage to the Estlink 2 submarine cable between Finland and Estonia [1] or the collision of the *Dali* container ship with the Baltimore bridge [2] highlight these risks. Another case is the collision of the ship *Petra L* with an offshore wind turbine [3]. Acoustic alarms were normally triggered when ships entered a 15-minute radius. As approximately 1000 alarms were triggered each week, the alarms were muted during the accident. Situation awareness [4] — understanding one’s own environment — is essential for the early detection of threats. The concept of situation awareness involves three phases that begin in the first phase with perceiving the environment what objects exist and where they are in the current situation. In the second phase, the current situation has to be mapped to understand how the objects are moving and whether there are anomalies or

threats in the environment, for example. The last phase is the projection of future states to predict where objects will be in the future, for example to predict threats for an infrastructure in the future. This requires a structured world model (WM) that represents internally the real world and captures objects such as actors, events, and situations to provide information for perceiving objects for a situation. This is the first phase of situation awareness to be able to assess or predict security-relevant situations in phases two and three later on.

Advances in machine learning (ML) offer new opportunities to improve situation awareness by identifying patterns in large, complex, and heterogeneous data sets, that are difficult for humans to grasp. These patterns help to recognize situations of interest. However, threats to maritime security are rare so training data are limited. A further challenge is that threats can be complex scenarios, i.e. situations that are influenced by various factors, dynamics, or in some cases unknown factors. This means that they cannot be easily recognized. An example of a complex safety situation is a drifting ship since different information and unknown variables are required to predict the future position such as the weather conditions (current, wind, waves), ship dimension, and ship draft. In addition, complex mathematical models or simulations are required to predict the behavior of the drifting ships, for which differential equations must be solved. For this reason, expert-based approaches such as Bayesian networks (BNs) or synthetic data must complement ML-based threat assessment approaches.

This paper describes the concept of a maritime WM that provides relevant information for expert-based or ML-based approaches to be able to assess threat scenarios based on data from the WM. The WM must flexibly select and process various data features depending on the specific threat scenario. Relevant data may include ship-related factors (e.g. location, speed, course, inspection history, and flag state) as well as weather and infrastructure conditions.

The paper is structured as follows. Section II presents the related work on existing WMs for the perception of objects

such as ships and the evaluation of situations based on ship movements. Section III describes the developed concept of a maritime WM that enables the perception of the environment. The presented WM provides several query-able interfaces to retrieve ship, weather, and infrastructure data. Finally, Section IV concludes this work and offers an outlook on future research directions.

II. EXISTING WORLD MODELS

Various WMs are used in different areas, including robotics [5]–[7]. In [5], an internal WM was designed to represent a robot’s perception of the real world. A review of multiple robot WMs established design guidelines in [6], defining a WM consisting of three components: Boundary, State, and Operations (adding, removing, or modifying data). The State internally represents the real world and is only accessible via two Boundary interfaces introduced in [7]: *tell* (to update the WM) and *ask* (to retrieve data directly, transformed, or abstractly).

In robotics, robots perceive the world with WMs and can use them to interact with the world. In contrast, maritime WMs support global situation monitoring by providing risk assessments and recommendations to avoid dangerous situations — for example, for ships or emergency services such as the coast guard. In contrast to threat assessment with flexible features, WMs for ship navigation or collision detection have fixed data features that must be evaluated. A maritime surveillance WM in [8] integrates real-time and static data from various data sources, including Automatic Identification System (AIS), satellite-based Synthetic Aperture Radar data, and airborne systems with radar and optical images. These data are consolidated via ontologies and integrated into a Real-Time Maritime Situation Awareness System using Ontology-Based Data Access, enabling relational data to be mapped to ontologies. User queries are executed in a Relational Database Management System like PostgreSQL to retrieve the data.

Another maritime WM in [9] pursues an object orientated approach to situation analysis. It has a receiving interface for observation data (e.g. AIS) and an access interface for situation analyses. Observations are assigned to existing objects using unique identifier as the International Maritime Organization (IMO) number. If the IMO number does not exist for the observation, a nearest-neighbor approach links them to existing objects. After a successful mapping to an existing object, a fusion manager merges each object attribute with a dedicated fusion module. Otherwise, an instance manager adds unassigned objects to the WM if they are frequently observed within a certain time frame. Moreover, the instance manager also removes objects from the WM if no observations are made for a certain period of time.

III. CONCEPT OF MARITIME WORLD MODEL

This section compares the WMs from [8], [9] and presents our requirements for a WM. The structure of our WM is then shown, how data are stored and how they can be accessed.

A. Comparison of Existing World Models and Requirements of Own World Model

The maritime WM of [9] provides a tell interface to provide information about the state of the WM, as recommended in [6]. Within the WM, the sensor data are fused and observations of known objects update the associated object attributes in their WM, but [8] does not show how data are inserted into the databases and how they are merged when needed. Since the data must be added to the database in [8], there will need to be an internal tell interface where the data are passed to the database with or without processing. As new data are constantly being added, the current status of an object can be queried using its last entry. The data storage differs between both WMs: [8] uses a database, while [9] follows an object-orientated approach. In both cases, observations can be retrieved via the ask interface, but [8] relies on ontology-based queries to a database, whereas [9] associates related observations in an object-orientated approach. A limitation of both models is that they do not include certain ship information, such as the flag state. Since data for threat scenarios are rare, synthetic data are required to evaluate assessment tools on them. Both WMs have no interface for this. For this reason, the new WM is designed to incorporate additional ship information and provide an tell interface for synthetic data from constructive simulations.

To assess situations with ML-based or expert-based approaches such as BNs, various data must be provided by the WM (cf. Figure 1): ship, weather, map, bathymetry, and infrastructure data. Additionally, synthetic data from constructive simulations should be also accessible. The ship data include position data such as ship position or speed and ship information such as the ship dimension or flag state. The weather data can be current, wind, or waves, for example. For the infrastructures, their geometries or locations can be retrieved as well as their features, for example, offshore wind turbines or power cables.

B. Structure for Data Storage

After comparing two WMs and the requirements for our own WM, our concept is presented and begins with its storage. Since the maritime WM monitors the state of the real world in the maritime domain, most of the data are already stored on data repositories or in databases. In the latter case, the database can be used as a basis to provide these data to the WM, as in [8], where a database is also used for the WM. This means that the existing structures are used to insert the data into the database, which then replaces the tell interface. In the first version of our WM, we use AIS and infrastructure data from Electronic Navigational Charts (ENCs) in a database and weather data including bathymetry data based on binary Network Common Data Form (NetCDF) files. This is a common file format for storing climate and weather data in compact storage space to handle multi-dimensional arrays, and the data can be accessed with multiple dimensions such as time, latitude, and longitude. Infrastructure data also includes map data, such as coastlines or navigation lines.

Fig. 1. The maritime world model provides various data for threat assessment. The data include ship data, which contain position and ship information data, weather data (current, wind, or waves, for example), map, bathymetry, and infrastructure data. Moreover, the world model should also process synthetic data from constructive simulations.

Weather data are only queried (such as wind speed, wind direction, current speed, current direction, wave height, wave direction, etc.) based on location and time. Since raw data are already stored in NetCDF files, the weather data are not additionally stored in a database. This reduces the storage space for the weather data. To enable quick access to the weather data, the corresponding NetCDF files are searched for weather information of interest based on time and location and k-dimensional trees optimize the data access. After that, the weather data are interpolated with an implementation similar to the open-source framework OpenDrift by [10].

The ship data are mostly available in AIS data stored in a PostgreSQL database. In this database, all kind of AIS message types are stored but the position, ship information, and voyage data are mainly of interest. The position data from the AIS position reports (cf. Table I: AIS messages from type one, two, and three) consist of features that indicate the ship location (latitude and longitude) with the corresponding timestamp. The course over ground is the movement direction and the true heading is the inclination in which the ship is aligned with the bow. Furthermore, the data contain also the speed and course how the ships are moving and can be identified by the unique Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI) number. The communication state is stored as an integer and can be retrieved as JSON string, since it concludes different values depending on how the AIS messages sent, either by Incremental Time Division Multiple Access (ITDMA) or Self-Organized Time Division Multiple Access (SOTDMA).

The AIS messages of type five contain ship information and voyage-related data (cf. Table II). The ship information data has features of the ship dimension (ship length and width), which can be calculated using the distances between the AIS antenna and the ship boundaries (bow, stern, port, and

TABLE I

FEATURES THAT CAN BE RETRIEVED FROM THE DATABASE FOR AIS MESSAGE FROM TYPE ONE, TWO, AND THREE. THE JSON STRING IS COMPOSED OF DIFFERENT VALUES OF THE COMMUNICATION STATE.

Feature	Data Type
timestamp	TIMESTAMP
latitude	DOUBLE
longitude	DOUBLE
message_type	SMALLINT
repeat_indicator	SMALLINT
mmsi	INTEGER
speed_over_ground	NUMERICAL(4,1)
course_over_ground	NUMERICAL(4,1)
navigational_status	SMALLINT
rate_of_turn	SMALLINT
position_accuracy	BOOLEAN
true_heading	SMALLINT
timestamp_sender	SMALLINT
maneuver_indicator	SMALLINT
spare	SMALLINT
raim_flag	BOOLEAN
communication_state	JSONB

starboard). In addition to the unique AIS MMSI number, ships contain a unique IMO number which, unlike the MMSI number, does not change if the ship owner changes, for example. The MMSI number can be used to merge position and ship information or voyage data. The ship draft normally only changes in ports and is therefore part of the voyage data instead of position data. The destination and estimated time of arrival are additional voyage data, but these data are entered manually and may therefore be out of date or incorrect.

To also consider other features such as flag states if they are available in our data according to the MMSI number, other ship information data from other data sources (cf. Table III) can be also accessed. Other features include the following information: in which year a ship was built, in which port the ship is registered, or what maximum weight a ship can carry, which is indicated by deadweight tonnage. The vessel type is also more detailed compared to the ship information data from the AIS reports, for instance whether a ship is a container ship or oil tanker.

Since no simulation environment has yet been chosen for the constructive simulation, it is not known which interfaces can be provided to transfer the synthetic data to the WM. Therefore, the tell interface will be developed later. If possible, the data should be transferred to the WM as a JSON context via a Representational State Transfer (REST) Application Programming Interface (API). The data are then stored in a separate database and should be retrieved via the same ask interfaces that are explained for the other data in the next paragraph. To run the constructive simulation in co-simulation with the WM, a new instance of the WM must be generated for each simulation run to access only the data from the current run.

C. Data Access via REST API

In addition to the tell interface, a WM requires also an ask interface, as mentioned in [7]. To simplify the access for

TABLE II
FEATURES THAT CAN BE RETRIEVED FROM THE DATABASE FOR AIS
MESSAGES FROM TYPE FIVE.

Feature	Data Type
timestamp	TIMESTAMP
mmsi	INTEGER
imo_number	INTEGER
ais_version	INTEGER
call_sign	VARCHAR(40)
vessel_name	VARCHAR(120)
ship_and_cargo_type	SMALLINT
to_bow	SMALLINT
to_stern	SMALLINT
to_port	SMALLINT
to_starboard	SMALLINT
ship_length	SMALLINT
ship_width	SMALLINT
draft	DOUBLE
estimated_time_of_arrival	TEXT
data_terminal_equipment	TEXT
destination	TEXT
type_of_electronic_position_fixing_device	SMALLINT

TABLE III
FEATURES THAT CAN BE RETRIEVED FROM THE DATABASE FROM OTHER
SOURCES THAN AIS IF THEY ARE AVAILABLE FOR SHIPS OF INTEREST.

Feature	Data Type
timestamp	TIMESTAMP
mmsi	INTEGER
imo	INTEGER
call_sign	VARCHAR(40)
vessel_name	VARCHAR(120)
vessel_type	VARCHAR(40)
year_of_build	SMALLINT
ship_length	DOUBLE
ship_width	DOUBLE
draft	DOUBLE
gross_tonnage	INTEGER
deadweight_tonnage	INTEGER
flag_state	CHAR(3)
port_of_registry	VARCHAR(20)
company_name	VARCHAR(100)

the ask interface, a clearly defined and flexible interface is provided via a REST API that processes data queries from the user. These queries are made using a JSON payload.

If only weather data are required to assess an infrastructure, the query format can be seen in Listing 1 to check whether it is possible to enter an offshore platform, for example. Lists of locations and timestamps can be passed for the query. Both lists must have the same length for the query to be valid. A location is a dictionary in which the latitude and longitude must be specified. Furthermore, weather features must be passed to the query to retrieve the data from the corresponding NetCDF files. If the interpolation is true, the two closest indices for each dimension are searched for and then combined. Therefore, $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 2 = 8$ positions are required for value interpolation if a feature has all three dimensions of timestamp, latitude, and longitude. Otherwise, the value from the nearest point is returned. In Listing 2, an example result is shown when two locations and timestamps as well

as the weather features wind speed and wind direction are passed as a query. Other examples of weather features are wave height, wave direction, current speed, or current direction. The response is a dictionary in which each element contains an equally long list of the passed locations and timestamps. The first three elements timestamp, latitude, longitude are standard elements and the remaining elements depend on the features passed to the query. In this case, the wind speed and wind direction are included in the result.

The format of the AIS data queries has a similar query compared to Listing 1 (cf. Listing 3). However, location boundaries instead of concrete locations are part of the query to search for ships in the area. Moreover, the time range is used to search for ships which are in the desired location area in a certain time range. The result of the request contains a dictionary with all passed AIS and weather features from the query (cf. Listing 4). In this example, speed over ground, IMO number are the AIS features, and wind speed, wind direction, and wave height are the weather features which are passed to query. Further AIS features can be found in Table I, Table II, and Table III. In each response, the timestamp, MMSI, latitude, and longitude are additional elements. By only passing features of interest, the user retrieve only data required for the specific use case. Each element of the dictionary has an equally long list, depending on how many ship locations are found in the AIS data for the passed location area of interest and time range. For this AIS and weather interface, the ship locations are first searched. After that, the weather data are requested for the locations and timestamps of the ships found. This request can be used to check whether a ship is approaching an offshore wind farm. Both interfaces (Listing 1 and Listing 3) can provide current or historical data, as the timestamp can be passed to the query. Therefore, the WM can later be used to evaluate threat assessment on past situations.

Listing 5 shows the query format for infrastructures to know where critical infrastructures are that need to be protected. The query contains the location boundaries to search all infrastructures in this area. The infrastructures can be limited by the infrastructure features. Moreover, additional information columns about the infrastructures can be accessed by the infrastructure columns such as name of the infrastructure or a unique id, for example. In Listing 6, an example response is shown in which the features, subfeatures, and geometry are standard elements of the result dictionary. The subfeature is required for submarine cables, for instance, since it can be either data cable or power cable. The list of geometry can contain different geometry types: point, line, or polygon. For this response, name and information must be passed to a query to retrieve these elements in the response. All three queries can be used to provide current situation information for threat assessment approaches. Therefore, we have developed a Python script which can update probabilities of BNs to assess attack scenarios for BNs which are developed in the future.

Listing 1. Weather data request

```
{
  "location": [{
    "latitude": float, "longitude": float
  }, ...],
  "timestamp": [datetime, ...],
  "weather_features": [str, ...],
  "interpolation": bool
}
```

Listing 2. Weather data response

```
{
  "timestamp": ["2025-09-05T09:00:00Z",
    "2025-09-05T09:00:00Z"],
  "latitude": [54.18, 54.2],
  "longitude": [7.89, 7.9],
  "wind_speed": [float, float],
  "wind_direction": [float, float]
}
```

Listing 3. AIS data request

```
{
  "location_bounds": {
    "north": float, "south": float,
    "west": float, "east": float
  },
  "time_range": [datetime, datetime],
  "ais_features": [str, ...],
  "weather_features": [str, ...]
}
```

Listing 4. AIS data response

```
{
  "timestamp": [datetime, datetime],
  "mmsi": [int, int],
  "latitude": [float, float],
  "longitude": [float, float],
  "speed_over_ground": [float, float],
  "imo_number": [float, float],
  "wind_speed": [float, float],
  "wind_direction": [float, float],
  "wave_height": [float, float]
}
```

Listing 5. Infrastructure data request

```
{
  "location_bounds": {
    "north": float, "south": float,
    "west": float, "east": float
  },
  "infrastructure_features": [str, ...],
  "infrastructure_columns": [str, ...]
}
```

Listing 6. Infrastructure data response

```
{
  "feature": ["wind_turbine",
    "cable_submarine",
    "offshore_production_area"],
  "subfeature": ["", "power_cable",
    "wind_farm"],
  "geometry": [point, line, polygon],
  "name": [str, str, str]
  "information": ["",
    "Alternating Current", ""]
}
```

IV. CONCLUSION

To summarize, a maritime world model concept has been developed with three interfaces to provide current or historical data from different data sources to evaluate later threat assessment tools on past situations. The three interfaces provide ship position and information data, weather data, and infrastructure data. The WM can be used to perceive situations, which is the first phase of the situational awareness concept. The second phase to interpret current situations and the third phase to predict future situations are not covered in this paper. In the future, threat assessment tools (expert-based approaches such as BNs or ML-based approaches) should be developed to determine whether current situations are threats for infrastructures. The WM is required to provide the necessary data for the threat assessment tools. Following the development of such tools, threat prediction should also be considered. Additionally, it should be investigated how the tell interface could be designed to integrate synthetic data when it is specified which interfaces the constructive simulation can provide. If the constructive simulation is performed as co-simulation in combination with the WM, only the data provided by the constructive simulation should be used by the threat assessment tools to return their results to the simulation. Therefore, a separate instance of the WM should be started for the simulation run.

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